

Effects of silica and phosphorus application on yield and phosphorus nutrition of rice

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We studied the effect of Si, with and without applied P, on yield and P nutrition of rice during 1984-86. Six treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Soil was sandy loam (Haplaquept) with pH 5.4, CEC 6.6 meq/100 g, 0.450% organic C, 3.5 ppm Olsen P, and 9.2 ppm available Si (NH₄OAC

extractable at pH 4.0). Rice husk containing 7.0% Si, 0.04% P, 0.33% N, and 1.05% K was applied 25 d before transplanting at 428 kg/ha, to supply 30 kg Si/ha. P at 8.7 and 13 kg/ha and 15 kg N, 24.9 kg K/ha were applied at transplanting of 25-d-old rice variety

Jajati. The crop was topdressed with 30 and 15 kg N/ha at 18 and 60 d after transplanting.

Maximum yield and P content of rice were obtained with 30 kg Si + 13 kg P/ha (see table). □

Effect of Si from rice husk and P on yield and P content of rice. ^a

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			P content (%)		
	1984 WS	1984-85 DS	1985-86 DS	1984 WS	1984-85 DS	1985-86 DS
Control	2.5	3.0	2.9	0.23	0.23	0.21
Rice husk (30 kg Si/ha)	2.6	3.4	3.8	0.28	0.30	0.30
8.7 kg P/ha	2.9	3.4	3.9	0.28	0.30	0.31
Rice husk + 8.7 kg P/ha	2.9	3.8	4.3	0.30	0.31	0.31
13 kg P/ha	3.0	3.9	4.0	0.30	0.31	0.31
Rice husk + 13 kg P/ha	3.2	4.4	4.4	0.31	0.31	0.31
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.01	0.00	0.01

^aDS = dry season, WS = wet season.

Effect of blue-green algae (BGA) on rice yield in Kashmir

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We tested the effect on rice yield of BGA inoculation with lime (500 kg/ha) and Mo (sodium molybdate, 0.5 kg/ha) at three levels of urea (30, 45, and 60 kg N/ha).

The experiment was conducted May-Oct 1985 and 1986 in the Kashmir Valley (average rainfall 285 mm, humidity 43-90%, temperature 8-36 °C). Soil was clay loam with pH 5.6, 1.82% organic C, 0.031 ppm available Mo, and CEC 18.2 meq/100 g. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Rice variety K39 was transplanted the 3d wk of Jun, 33 d after sowing. Lime and Mo were applied during field preparation. N as urea was applied 10% at transplanting, 25% at panicle initiation, and 25% at flowering. P as single superphosphate at 45 kg P/ha

and K as muriate of potash at 20 kg K/ha were applied as basal.

BGA inoculum, a mixture of *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*, *Aulosira*, and *Tolypothrix*, was prepared by open air soil culture method. The soil was inoculated with 10 kg BGA culture/ha 1 wk after transplanting.

At low N levels, BGA inoculation

alone significantly increased yield (see table). Adding lime and Mo with BGA significantly increased yields at 30 and 45 kg N.

BGA proliferated in the plots where lime and Mo were applied. That contributed to a yield increase equivalent to 15 kg N/ha under the temperate conditions of Kashmir. □

Effect of BGA inoculation on rice yield in Kashmir, 1985-86. ^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)						Straw yield (t/ha)					
	1985			1986			1985			1986		
	30 N	45 N	60 N	30 N	45 N	60 N	30 N	45 N	60 N	30 N	45 N	60 N
Control	6.2	6.8	7.4	4.6	5.5	6.0	7.4	7.9	8.4	5.3	5.6	6.2
Lime + Mo	6.4	7.0	7.5	4.8	5.6	6.2	7.5	8.1	8.5	5.2	5.8	6.4
BGA	6.9	7.5	7.8	5.4	6.1	6.5	8.0	8.5	8.6	5.7	6.2	6.8
Lime + Mo + BGA	7.3	7.8	7.9	5.8	6.3	6.5	8.4	8.8	8.8	6.0	6.3	6.9
LSD at 0.05												
BGA culture (C)	0.2			0.2			0.2			0.2		
Nitrogen (N)	0.2			0.2			0.2			0.2		
Interaction (C × N)	0.4			0.3			0.3			0.4		

^aMean of three replications.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.